

How to submit your first paper

Practical tips, tricks and common mistakes for new PhD students and aspiring researchers

Preamble

Why publish?

Why publishing is necessary

- Primary channel of sharing research results
- Receiving feedback from peers
- Contribution to the research field
- Only quantifiable metric to *measure* progress

Without publishing the scientific community would consist of individuals, working only by themselves, probably on exactly the same redundant problems.

Venues: Conference vs Journal

- Typically once a year
- Faster review cycles
- Strict deadlines
- Shorter format
- Presentations of work at conference

Quality Types:

A*, A, B, C, *unranked*

- Continuous nature
- Longer review cycles
- No deadlines
- More space and longer formats
- No presentations

Quality Types:

Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4

Picking the right venue

Depending on...

- Scope
- Audience
- Acceptance
- Reputation
- Timeline

Tip #1

Your supervisor or scientific mentor is most likely very familiar with his/her community and their related venues.

Don't be afraid to ask for help on determining a target venue.

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Where to start

and when...

When to start? - NOW!

No matter the current stage of your current project one can always start writing a draft.

Benefits of writing drafts early:

- Practical experience of scientific writing
- Battling writer's block early on
- Ability to ask for reviews (and improve)

Tip #2

Drafting makes scientific writing substantially less intimidating, especially in the beginning.

Write your first drafts for yourself (and use them as practice)

Where to write?

There are many freely available conference and journal [LaTeX](#) templates that you can use to practice.

A few examples:

- [ACM Conference Proceedings Primary Article Template](#)
- [Springer Nature LaTeX Template](#)
- [IEEE Conference Template](#)
- [Elsevir Astronomy & Computing journal template](#)

Tip #3

Most LaTeX templates are interchangeable with minimal editorial effort.

Always double-check that you are using the correct format before submission.

Paper Structure

How papers are organized

Common chapters found in papers

- **Abstract** (150-250 word summary)
- **Introduction** (Preamble to your work)
- **Background** (Required knowledge to understand your work)
- **Related Work** (What works does yours compare to?)
- **Methodology** (What methods did you apply)
- **Results** (Your main findings and results)
- **Discussion** (Interpretation of results)
- **Conclusion** (Summarization of your key findings)
- **Ethical Statement** (Ethical implications of your work)
- **Acknowledgement** (Funding information)

Tip #4

Scout some accepted papers of your target venues.

They usually follow similar patterns, which will help you set the correct emphases on most important chapters.

Writing Tips

How to start writing

How to start your draft

There is no right or wrong in drafting.

Drafting can start:

- as a list of keywords for a chapter
- as a mind map with linked keywords
- as hand-drawn sketches for figures
- as a skeleton document filled with Lorem Ipsum text
- as a list of contributions

Tip #5

A common way to start writing is to create a list of keywords.

As next steps you transform these keywords into sentences - and the sentences into paragraphs.

Common beginner mistakes

- Writing too vaguely ("*some* results show...")
- Not clearly stating contributions
- Weak related work section (position your work)
- Ignoring formatting guidelines (might lead to desk rejection)
- Time planning issues (rushing a paper towards a deadline)

Citations - Why do we use them?

Citations have a quintessential role in academic writing.

Reasons to cite:

- Give credit (acknowledge authors, avoid plagiarism)
- Support your claims (statements backed by existing research)
- Position your work (how your work fits into the current state of the field)
- Enable verification (readers can check sources)
- Guide further reading (help others explore)

Citations - Example

Example for a claim:

“Deep learning performs well on images.”

Example for a claim backed by a citation:

“Deep learning performs well on images (Krizhevsky et al., 2012).”

Source: [\[Krizhevsky et al., 2012\]](#)

Figures in scientific papers

Figures communicate complex ideas quickly and clearly.

A good figure can replace paragraphs of text.

Highlight key findings and what matters most.

What makes a figure good?

- Clear and Readable (labels, fonts, resolution)
- Self-contained (understandable with caption alone)
- Honest representations (faithful scales and visuals)
- Consistency (keep color and formatting schemes across figures)

Tip #6

Alongside your abstract, your figures are the first thing reviewers look at during reviews.

At this point reviewers already decide whether they look forward to reading your paper.

Invest enough time and leave a good impression.

Figures - Common Mistakes

A reader should be able to understand your figure (+ caption) without reading the entire paper.

Common mistakes include:

- Overly complex and cluttered (2 figures in one)
- Missing labels or units (becomes ambiguous)
- Small text & low resolution (becomes unreadable)
- Misleading scaling or cherry-picking (unfair representation)

A weak figure can kill the strongest paper.

Reproducibility and Open Science

Open Science: Making research transparent, accessible and reusable

Reproducibility: Others can obtain the same results using your data and methods

Why?

Builds trust, Improves research quality, accelerates progress, and increases visibility

How?

Share code e.g., on GitHub, share data e.g., with Zenodo, and document methods clearly e.g., using fixed random seeds

Reproducibility checklist

- Code available?**
- Data available? (if possible)**
- Environment described? (libraries & versions)**
- Random seeds fixed?**
- Hyperparameters specified?**
- ... are there any additional requirements necessary for your research field

Defining your contribution

Common pitfall for novice researchers.

What counts as a contribution?

- New method
- Improvement
- Benchmarking

Your contributions must be clearly stated and understandable.

Tip #7

Contributions are typically stated in a bullet-point format, commonly placed in the introduction section.

In scientific writing, your contributions are your selling points.

Conclusion

To summarize

Realistic Timeline

People underestimate time.

The average time for an A* paper from the initial idea to the final paper submission is approximately 9 months (excluding the reviewing process).

An estimation for writing is:

- Writing: 2-6 weeks (depending on experience)
- Internal reviews: 2-4 weeks (depending on availability)
- (Submission → Decision: 1-6 months)

What happens after writing?

After the writing process concludes and your final paper is ready, your next step is to look for a fitting venue (if not decided beforehand). After formatting you submit your paper to the chosen target venue and ...

- a) are desk rejected (you did not follow the venue's guidelines)
- b) get peer reviewed (open, single/double-blind)
 - i) and rejected (not novel enough, insufficient contribution)
 - ii) minor or major revisions (apply requested changes)
 - iii) and accepted :)

Further Reading

- “How to do good research, get it published in SIGKDD and get it cited!” - Eamonn Keogh [Link](#)
- Scientific Writing 2.0 - Jean-Luc Lebrun & Justin Lebrun [Link](#)
- Scientific Writing 3.0 - Jean-Luc Lebrun & Justin Lebrun [Link](#)

Credits

Special thanks to all the people who made and released these awesome resources for free:

- Presentation template by [SlidesCarnival](#)